

Three-dimensional hydrogen-bonded supramolecular networks assembled by lanthanide picrates and 4,4'-bipyridine

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The reactions of rare earth picrates with 4,4'-bpy in H₂O-CH₃CN give compounds [Tm(H₂O)₄(pic)₂]₂[Tm(H₂O)₆(pic)](4,4'-bpyH)₂(4,4'-bpy)₅(pic)₆ (**1**) and [Gd₂(4,4'-bpy)(pic)₂(H₂O)₁₂](4,4'-bpy)₅(H₂O)₆(pic)₄ (**2**) (4,4'-bpy = 4,4'-bipyridine, pic⁻ = picric anion). A supramolecular unit cell of compound **1** is assembled by intermolecular hydrogen bond from three independent complex cations which are crystallographically distinguishable. Such units are bridged in the form of side-by-side by 4,4'-bpy molecules via hydrogen bond to form stair-like chains, and then an elegant 2D-network structure. Furthermore, a supramolecular 3D-network is constructed by hydrogen bond formed by uncoordinated picric anion and coordinated water molecules. Both coordinative and hydrogen bonds contribute to networking in compound **2** based on 4,4'-bpy-bridged binuclear units which have been shown to be linked in the form of head-to-tail by double hydrogen-bond bridges of the type Gd-H₂O...4,4'-bpy...H₂O...H₂O-Gd, producing zig-zag chains. The chains are further extended into hydrogen-bonded 3D-network. This generates supramolecular cavities which incorporate some uncoordinated picric anions and 4,4'-bpy as guests via host-guest hydrogen bonding. Magnetic susceptibilities measured for compound **2** from 75 to 300 K are indicative of no appreciable magnetic exchange interaction between the adjacent Gd^{III} ions.

For more than 150 years, chemists were predominantly concerned with the nature of the covalent bond in organic molecules or complex molecules. Today, the nature of non-covalent bond has advanced to the center of interest in organic or inorganic chemistry¹. The fascinating and dynamic supramolecular research area is recognized as an intellectual and technological frontier in chemistry. However, incorporation of coordinate bonds into the supramolecular self-assembly triggered the development of an entirely new field in which organic and inorganic chemistry are completely scrambled. In the 1990s, the metal-directed self-assembly has been showing remarkable potentials to construct supramolecular architectures such as helices², grids³, boxes⁴, rods⁵, tubes⁶, interlocked systems⁷, and so on. The present work is concerned with the zeolite supramolecular complexes. The guest molecules should be kept in internal cavities, which may be constructed by using intermolecular interactions such as hydrogen bonding⁸ and metal coordination⁹. Supramolecular synthesis is analogous to molecular synthesis except those weak non-covalent bond interactions control the structure of the solid state. This has led to numerous molecular crystals exhibiting properties normally associated with conventional elemental and inorganic solids, including nonlinear optical behavior, electrical conductivity, superconductivity, ferromagnetism and clathration¹⁰.

We have recently synthesized two sorts of supramo-

lecular compounds having extensive 3D hydrogen-bonded network, which are rarely reported.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 contains the crystallographic data and further details of the X-ray structural determinations. Selected bond lengths and bond angles are listed in Table 2. The hydrogen bonds for compounds **1** and **2** are given in Table 3.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for compounds **1** and **2**

	Compd. 1	Compd. 2
Empirical formula	C ₁₃₆ H ₁₀₈ N ₄₇ O ₉₁ Tm ₃	C ₉₆ H ₉₆ N ₃₀ O ₆₀ Gd ₂
Crystal system	Triclinic	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 1	<i>P</i> 1̄
Color/habit	Yellow, needle	Yellow, needle
<i>a</i> , Å	15.1620(2)	8.1620(10)
<i>b</i> , Å	15.393(2)	14.877(2)
<i>c</i> , Å	21.316(4)	24.546(4)
α , deg	70.240(10)	93.520(10)
β , deg	73.370(10)	91.2550(10)
γ , deg	62.590(10)	100.410(10)
<i>V</i> , Å ³	4104.8(11)	2924.3(7)
Formula weight	4363.48	2944.52
λ , Å	0.71073	0.71073
<i>Z</i>	1	2
<i>D</i> _x , g cm ⁻³	1.765	1.672
<i>F</i> (000)	2188	1490
Crystal size, mm	0.64 × 0.50 × 0.48	0.36 × 0.34 × 0.26
<i>T</i> , K	296	291(2)
θ	1.53° < θ < 28.50°	1.58° < θ < 25.01°
Index range	-3 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 20, -17 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 19, -27 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 28	0 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 9, -17 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 17, -29 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 29
μ , min ⁻¹	1.735	1.241

Table-1 (contd.)

Refl. collected/unique	26330/25507	11470/10311
Max. and min. transm.	0.4927 and 0.4426	0.7767 and 0.6908
Refinement method	Full-matrix-block least-squares on F^2	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Parameters	2494	930
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	0.929	0.948
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.0316$, $\omega R_2 = 0.0661$	$R_1 = 0.0283$, $\omega R_2 = 0.0591$
R indices (all data)	$R_1 = 0.0394$, $\omega R_2 = 0.0678$	$R_1 = 0.0369$, $\omega R_2 = 0.0609$
Largest diff. peak and hole, $e/\text{\AA}^3$	1.037 and -0.807	0.368 and -0.439
Δ/σ	0.002	0.001
ω	$1/[\sigma^2(F_0)^2 + (0.0395P)^2]$	$1/[\sigma^2(F_0)^2 + (0.0315P)^2]$

The reactions between rare earth metal picrates and 4,4'-bipyridine in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN-H}_2\text{O}$ (1 : 1) gave a small amount of precipitate. These compounds are found to be soluble in solvents such as CH_3CN , CH_3COCH_3 , $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$, but very difficult to dissolve in H_2O . Suitable crystals of them were not easy to obtain for a single crystal X-ray diffraction. The result of the X-ray diffraction indicates that there are some protonized 4,4'-bpy existing in compound 1. This is caused by the thulium picrate which was not thoroughly purified. The solution of thulium picrate in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN-H}_2\text{O}$ (1 : 1) has the pH value of 4. In this acid environment, some 4,4'-bipyridine molecules are easily protonized.

Table 2. Bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for compounds 1 and 2

Compound 1 :					
Tm(1)-O(8)	2.211(3)	Tm(3)-O(37)	2.241(4)	Tm(2)-O(19)	2.247(4)
Tm(1)-O(17)	2.310(3)	Tm(3)-O(47)	2.319(4)	Tm(2)-O(33)	2.313(4)
Tm(1)-O(18)	2.329(3)	Tm(3)-O(48)	2.334(4)	Tm(2)-O(36)	2.366(4)
Tm(1)-O(14)	2.430(3)	Tm(3)-O(49)	2.336(3)	Tm(2)-O(27)	2.512(4)
Tm(2)-O(26)	2.216(4)	Tm(1)-O(1)	2.235(3)	Tm(3)-O(46)	2.318(4)
Tm(2)-O(35)	2.310(4)	Tm(1)-O(16)	2.315(3)	Tm(3)-O(44)	2.323(3)
Tm(2)-O(34)	2.331(4)	Tm(1)-O(15)	2.356(3)	Tm(3)-O(45)	2.335(3)
Tm(2)-O(20)	2.430(4)	Tm(1)-O(2)	2.476(4)	Tm(3)-O(38)	2.455(4)
O(8)-Tm(1)-O(1)	89.30(13)	O(37)-Tm(3)-O(46)	139.24(14)	O(26)-Tm(2)-O(35)	98.52(14)
O(1)-Tm(1)-O(17)	105.65(13)	O(46)-Tm(3)-O(47)	71.59(14)	O(26)-Tm(2)-O(33)	94.15(15)
O(1)-Tm(1)-O(16)	140.12(13)	O(46)-Tm(3)-O(44)	73.34(13)	O(35)-Tm(2)-O(33)	142.07(14)
O(8)-Tm(1)-O(18)	82.18(13)	O(37)-Tm(3)-O(48)	107.16(17)	O(19)-Tm(2)-O(34)	79.42(11)
O(17)-Tm(1)-O(18)	73.96(12)	O(47)-Tm(3)-O(48)	82.61(16)	O(33)-Tm(2)-O(34)	142.67(13)
O(8)-Tm(1)-O(15)	72.53(13)	O(37)-Tm(3)-O(45)	80.24(14)	O(19)-Tm(2)-O(36)	138.73(10)
O(17)-Tm(1)-O(15)	137.31(12)	O(47)-Tm(3)-O(45)	75.94(14)	O(33)-Tm(2)-O(36)	72.68(13)
O(18)-Tm(1)-O(15)	145.07(11)	O(48)-Tm(3)-O(45)	144.94(14)	O(26)-Tm(2)-O(20)	149.47(10)
O(1)-Tm(1)-O(14)	148.49(12)	O(46)-Tm(3)-O(49)	137.33(14)	O(35)-Tm(2)-O(20)	74.89(10)
O(16)-Tm(1)-O(14)	70.93(12)	O(44)-Tm(3)-O(49)	147.74(13)	O(34)-Tm(2)-O(20)	125.14(11)
O(15)-Tm(1)-O(14)	116.60(12)	O(45)-Tm(3)-O(49)	76.06(13)	O(26)-Tm(2)-O(27)	69.38(14)
O(1)-Tm(1)-O(2)	68.19(12)	O(46)-Tm(3)-O(38)	73.93(14)	O(35)-Tm(2)-O(27)	149.65(14)
O(16)-Tm(1)-O(2)	76.23(12)	O(44)-Tm(3)-O(38)	77.05(14)	O(34)-Tm(2)-O(27)	75.42(14)
O(15)-Tm(1)-O(2)	71.91(13)	O(45)-Tm(3)-O(38)	139.93(14)	O(20)-Tm(2)-O(27)	129.41(10)
O(26)-Tm(2)-O(19)	139.14(10)	O(8)-Tm(1)-O(17)	148.35(13)	O(37)-Tm(3)-O(47)	149.03(13)
O(19)-Tm(2)-O(35)	109.42(10)	O(8)-Tm(1)-O(16)	108.69(13)	O(37)-Tm(3)-O(44)	84.42(14)
O(19)-Tm(2)-O(33)	81.94(10)	O(17)-Tm(1)-O(16)	77.58(12)	O(47)-Tm(3)-O(44)	198.39(15)
O(26)-Tm(2)-O(34)	79.75(15)	O(1)-Tm(1)-O(18)	78.59(12)	O(46)-Tm(3)-O(48)	72.00(15)
O(35)-Tm(2)-O(34)	75.04(14)	O(16)-Tm(1)-O(18)	137.55(12)	O(44)-Tm(3)-O(48)	137.74(13)
O(26)-Tm(2)-O(36)	75.92(13)	O(1)-Tm(1)-O(15)	77.43(13)	O(46)-Tm(3)-O(45)	124.67(15)
O(35)-Tm(2)-O(36)	76.01(13)	O(16)-Tm(1)-O(15)	74.84(12)	O(44)-Tm(3)-O(45)	76.16(13)
O(34)-Tm(2)-O(36)	138.56(14)	O(8)-Tm(1)-O(14)	70.45(12)	O(37)-Tm(3)-O(49)	75.00(14)
O(19)-Tm(2)-O(20)	69.02(13)	O(17)-Tm(1)-O(14)	83.31(12)	O(47)-Tm(3)-O(49)	80.22(14)
O(33)-Tm(2)-O(20)	76.13(11)	O(18)-Tm(1)-O(14)	75.01(12)	O(48)-Tm(3)-O(49)	73.17(14)
O(36)-Tm(2)-O(20)	73.56(9)	O(8)-Tm(1)-O(2)	141.17(13)	O(37)-Tm(3)-O(38)	67.95(14)
O(19)-Tm(2)-O(27)	71.54(10)	O(17)-Tm(1)-O(2)	70.30(12)	O(47)-Tm(3)-O(38)	141.46(13)
O(33)-Tm(2)-O(27)	68.07(14)	O(18)-Tm(1)-O(2)	120.99(13)	O(48)-Tm(3)-O(38)	70.73(15)
O(36)-Tm(2)-O(27)	124.31(13)	O(14)-Tm(1)-O(2)	141.17(13)	O(49)-Tm(3)-O(38)	116.04(15)
Compound 2 :					
Gd-O(1)	2.3144(19)	Gd-O(8)	2.422(2)	Gd-O(10)	2.413(2)
Gd-O(9)	2.396(2)	Gd-O(12)	2.342(2)	Gd-N(1)	2.625(2)
Gd-O(13)	2.411(2)	Gd-O(11)	2.398(2)		
O(1)-Gd-O(12)	77.56(8)	O(12)-Gd-N(1)	72.36(8)	O(11)-Gd-O(10)	71.37(8)
O(12)-Gd-O(9)	124.60(8)	O(11)-Gd-N(1)	139.91(8)	O(1)-Gd-O(8)	71.83(8)
O(12)-Gd-O(11)	145.86(8)	O(10)-Gd-N(1)	148.45(7)	O(9)-Gd-O(8)	73.87(8)
O(1)-Gd-O(13)	144.85(8)	C(6)-O(1)-Gd	139.63(19)	O(13)-Gd-O(8)	142.98(8)
O(9)-Gd-O(13)	69.98(8)	C(5)-N(1)-Gd	120.3(2)	O(1)-Gd-N(1)	94.38(7)
O(1)-Gd-O(10)	76.40(7)	O(1)-Gd-O(9)	145.10(8)	O(9)-Gd-N(1)	71.56(7)
O(9)-Gd-O(10)	131.24(8)	O(1)-Gd-O(11)	104.31(8)	O(13)-Gd-N(1)	98.65(9)
O(13)-Gd-O(10)	75.47(8)	O(9)-Gd-O(11)	72.96(8)	O(8)-Gd-N(1)	76.90(8)
O(12)-Gd-O(8)	134.24(8)	O(12)-Gd-O(13)	75.61(9)	C(5)-N(1)-C(1)	115.7(3)
O(11)-Gd-O(8)	75.85(8)	O(11)-Gd-O(13)	86.15(9)	C(1)-N(1)-Gd	123.6(2)
O(10)-Gd-O(8)	126.17(8)	O(12)-Gd-O(10)	76.18(8)		

Table 3. Hydrogen bond for compounds 1 and 2

Compound 1 :								
O16-H...N37	1555	2.735	O45-H...O57	1555	2.960	O36-H...O71	1555	2.733
O16-H...O50	1555	2.850	O44-H...N45	1555	2.696	O36-H...O77	1555	2.799
O17-H...N34	1545	2.727	O44-H...O78	1555	2.830	O36-H...O86	1555	2.834
O17-H...O64	1555	2.801	O45-H...N40	1645	2.798	O46-H...O78	1555	2.511
O18-H...N35	1555	2.834	O47-H...N44	1455	2.790	O46-H...O79	1555	2.765
O18-H...N42	1555	2.749	O47-H...O63	1555	2.750	O49-H...O72	1555	2.923
O33-H...N47	1555	2.631	O48-H...N41	1555	2.837	O49-H...O85	1555	2.784
O33-H...O85	1555	2.998	O48-H...O85	1555	2.874	O49-H...O91	1555	2.855
O34-H...O38	1555	2.750	O15-H...O50	1555	2.748	O77-H...N46	1645	2.858
O34-H...O65	1456	2.913	O15-H...O56	1555	2.903	O45-H...O58	1555	3.004
O35-H...N39	1565	2.742	O15-H...O57	1555	2.892			
O35-H...O64	1456	2.786	O57-H...N36	1645	2.806			
Compound 2 :								
O10-H...N7	1555	2.765	O13-H...O28	1455	2.775	O9-H...O21	1555	2.727
O10-H...O14	1555	2.907	O28-H...O14	1655	2.862	O29-H...O30	1555	2.820
O12-H...N9	1555	2.633	O28-H...N8	2666	2.812	O8-H...O28	1555	2.738
O12-H...O14	1555	2.687	O29-H...O4	1455	2.870	O8-H...O20	1655	2.965
O11-H...N5	1555	2.725	O30-H...O21	1565	2.890	O9-H...O29	1645	2.668
O13-H...O21	1555	2.777	O30-H...O17	1555	2.903			

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of compound 1, showing the atom numbering scheme.

IR spectra : The broad IR absorption bands for ν_{HOH} at 3380 (compound 1) and 3395 cm^{-1} (compound 2) indicate the presence of a water molecule as well as hydrogen bonding in both the compounds¹¹ 1 and 2. The presence of bands at 1609, 1539, 1412, 1215, 1082, 800, 625 cm^{-1} (for compound 1) and 1609, 1539, 1412, 1222, 1082, 800, 625 cm^{-1} (for compound 2) indicates that some 4,4'-bipyridine molecules exist as non-coordinated molecules¹².

Structure of $[\text{Tm}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{pic})_2]_2[\text{Tm}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6(\text{pic})](4,4'\text{-bpyH})_2(4,4'\text{-bpy})_3(\text{pic})_6$: Shown in Fig. 1, the crystal structure of compound 1 consists of a $[\text{Tm}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6(\text{pic})]^{2+}$ cation, two $[\text{Tm}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{pic})_2]^+$ cations, six pic^- anions and seven uncoordinated 4,4'-bpy molecules in which two are protonized. Three Tm^{III} centers lying at the corner of a triangle with different Tm...Tm separations (Tm1...Tm2 : 7.295 Å, Tm2...Tm3 : 7.897, Tm3...Tm1 : 9.065 Å) are crys-

Fig. 2. Schematic view of the hydrogen-bonded three-dimensional network for compound 1.

tallographically distinguishable with different guest environments. In $[\text{Tm}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6(\text{pic})]^{2+}$, the Tm^{III} ion is eight-coordinated by six oxygen atoms from water molecules and one deprotonated hydroxyl oxygen atom, one oxygen atom of the nitro-group in the picric anions, forming a distorted square anti-prismatic coordination polyhedron with the bond lengths of Tm-O in the range of 2.241(4)–2.455 Å. While in $[\text{Tm}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{pic})_2]^+$, the Tm^{III} ion is eight-coordinated by four oxygen atoms from water molecules and two deprotonated hydroxyl oxygen atoms, two oxygen atoms of the nitro-group in the picric anions, forming a distorted square anti-prismatic coordination polyhedron with the bond lengths of Tm-O in the range of 2.211(3)–2.476(4) (for Tm1) and 2.216–2.512 Å (for Tm3). In the

three coordination cations, all the coordinated picric anions afford one deprotonated hydroxyl oxygen atom and one nitro-oxygen atom to coordinate to Tm^{III} ion forming a stable six-membered cycle. The uncoordinated picric anions have interactions with the coordination cations through hydrogen bonds. Among them, three picric anions act as hydrogen-bonded bridge, bridging Tm1 and Tm3 (O47-H...O63 : 2.750, O57-H...O15 : 2.892, O45-H...O58 : 3.004, O45-H...O57 : 2.960 Å), Tm2 and Tm3 (O33-H...O85 : 2.998, O86-H...O36 : 2.834, O48-H...O85 : 2.874, O49-H...O85 : 2.784, O49-H...O91 : 2.855, O36-H...O71 : 2.733, O72-H...O49 : 2.923, O36-H...O77 : 2.799 Å), respectively. Thus a supramolecular unit is constructed, in which all the 4,4'-bipyridine molecules have interactions with coordination cations only by forming hydrogen bonds with coordinated water molecules. But there is no 4,4'-bipyridine molecule acting as hydrogen-bonded bridging to bridge different Tm^{III} ions in one supramolecular unit. A unit cell contains only one supramolecular unit.

Fig. 3. Crystal packing of compound 1.

The above supramolecular unit cell packs in the three-dimensional directions through all sorts of hydrogen bonds, as shown in Figs. 2 and 3. Along the *b*-axis, supramolecular cells are bridged into a one-dimensional stairs by forming hydrogen bonds (Tm1-O17-H...N34 (4,4'-bpy) N35...H-O18-Tm1, Tm2-O34-H...N38 (4,4'-bpy) N39...H-O35-Tm2). The stairs are bridged into a two-dimensional network in the form of face-to-face by uncoordinated 4,4'-

Fig. 4. Crystal structure of compound 2, showing the atom numbering scheme.

bipyridine molecule through hydrogen bond with coordinated water molecules (Tm3-O47-H...N44 (4,4'-bpy) N45...H-O44-Tm3) along *a*-axis.

At the same time, Tm(3) ions lying in the direction of the diagonal line are also connected via hydrogen bonds formed by 4,4'-bipyridine molecules with coordinated water molecules (Tm3-O45-H...N40 (4,4'-bpy) N41...H-O48-Tm3), further stabilizing the network. While the 2D-network packs along the *c*-direction, Tm2 and Tm1 coming from different network have weak interaction through hydrogen bond among the hydroxyl oxygen atom of picric anion and coordinated water molecules (O17-H...O64 : 2.801, O34-H...O65 : 2.913, O35-H...O64 : 2.786 Å), so formed an elegant 3D-hydrogen-bonded supramolecular network, in which the Tm1...Tm1, Tm2...Tm2 and Tm3...Tm3 separations between the nearest-neighbor units are all 15.160 Å.

Structure of [Gd₂(4,4'-bpy)(pic)₂(H₂O)₁₂](4,4'-bpy)₅(H₂O)₆(pic)₄ : The structure of compound 2 is made up of units of [Gd₂(4,4'-bpy)(pic)₂(H₂O)₁₂](4,4'-bpy)₅(H₂O)₆(pic)₄, with 188 non-hydrogen independent atoms (Fig. 4). Every Gd^{III} center coordinates to one nitrogen atom from 4,4'-bipyridine molecule, one oxygen atom from picric anion and six

Fig. 5. Crystal packing in plane (100) of compound 2, showing the formation of hydrogen bonding 2D-network.

water molecules to form a distorted trigonal dodecahedral environment. The bond length of the Gd-O (2.314(19)–2.422(2) Å) and Gd-N (2.625(2) Å) is a little shorter than those of the reported complex cation $[(\mu\text{-}4,4'\text{-bpy})\text{Nd}_2(\text{NO}_3)_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2-}$ (Nd-O : 2.429(7)–2.611(6), Nd-N : 2.701(6) Å)¹³. Perhaps it is caused by the lanthanide contraction. Two Gd^{III} ions are bridged by a coordinated 4,4'-bipyridine molecule to form a center symmetric complex cation $[\text{Gd}_2(4,4'\text{-bpy})(\text{pic})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{12}]^{4+}$ with the Gd...Gd distance of 12.325 Å. Similar to compound **1**, the uncoordinated 4,4'-bipyridine molecules only have interactions with the coordination cations by forming hydrogen bond with the coordinated water molecules (N5...H-O11 : 2.725(4), N7...H-O10 : 2.765(3), N9...H-O12 : 2.633(3) Å). In compound **1**, the six-membered cycle is formed when the picric anion coordinated to Tm^{III} ion, while in compound **2**, the picric anion is coordinated to Tm^{III} ion only by its hydroxyl oxygen.

A very interesting structural feature is that adjacent units are interconnected in the form of head-to-tail by hydrogen-bond bridges of the type Gd-O10-H...N7 (4,4'-bpy) N8...H-O28...H-O13-Gd (O10-H...N7 : 2.765(3), N8...H-O28 : 2.812(4), O28...H-O13 : 2.775(3) Å), as illustrated in Fig. 5. These hydrogen bonds extend the unit into a zig-zag chain running parallel to the line produced by two intersecting planes (100) and (011), with zig-zag undulation in the (100) plane (Fig. 6). Parallel zig-zag chains form 2D-layers parallel to the *bc*-plane by hydrogen bond (O28...H-O8 : 2.738(3) Å) between coordinated water molecules and uncoordinated water molecules coming from the adjacent chains along axis-*b*. When the two-dimensional network packs along axis-*a*, hydrogen bonds are formed between coordinated water molecules and uncoordinated water molecules (O29...H-O9 : 2.668(3) Å), uncoordinated water molecules and nitro-oxygen atoms of the coordinated picric anions (O29...H-O4 : 2.870(3) Å), to further extend the two-dimensional hydrogen-bonded network into a three-dimensional hydrogen-bonded supramolecular

Fig. 6. Crystal packing of compound **2**

network (Fig. 6).

As depicted in Fig. 7, an extensive hydrogen-bonded quasi-square supramolecular cavity is formed by four-coordinated cation and some uncoordinated water molecules, 4,4'-bipyridine molecules and picric anions. Other uncoordinated picric anion and 4,4'-bipyridine molecules are clathrated in the supramolecular cavities as guests via hydrogen bond with the coordinated water molecules of the host and further stabilize the cavities.

Fig. 7. Supramolecular cavity in compound **2**

Magnetic properties of the compound 2 : The effective magnetic moments of $[\text{Gd}_2(4,4'\text{-bpy})(\text{pic})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{12}](4,4'\text{-bpy})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6(\text{pic})_4$ are 10.85 B.M. (300 K) corresponding to an $s = 7/2$ state with an appreciable orbital contribution. And its magnetic susceptibility as a function of temperature (75–300 K) was measured. The temperature-dependence of the magnetic susceptibilities obeys the Curie-Weiss law : $\chi_m = C/(T - \theta)$, where $C = 15.00 \text{ emu K mol}^{-1}$ and $\theta = 0 \text{ K}$. Thus there is practically no magnetic exchange interaction between the neighboring Gd^{III} ions through 4,4'-bpy bridge. The magnetic interaction through the 4,4'-bpy bridge is usually very weak considering the long M...M distance. And it is reported that this interaction could be further reduced because of the twist of the two pyridine rings¹⁴.

Conclusion : Two novel hydrogen-bonded supramolecular polymers formed by rare earth picrates and 4,4'-bpy have been prepared and characterized : $[\text{Tm}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{pic})_2]_2$ $[\text{Tm}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6(\text{pic})](4,4'\text{-bpy})_2(4,4'\text{-bpy})_5(\text{pic})_6$ (**1**) and $[\text{Gd}_2(4,4'\text{-bpy})(\text{pic})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{12}](4,4'\text{-bpy})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6(\text{pic})_4$ (**2**). There are two types of association models for the 4,4'-bpy ligand in the crystal as in **2**. One is a coordination bridge between the gadolinium centers to form centrosymmetric binuclear coordination cations. The other is a hydrogen bonding type and bridges the coordinated H₂O molecules in the nearest neighbor coordination cations together with the uncoor-

minated H₂O molecules to construct a zig-zag chain. While in compound **1**, only the hydrogen bonding type of association mode is found and bridges the coordinated H₂O molecules to form stair-like chain, and even 2-D network. This can be attributed to the different coordination abilities of rare earth metals to 4,4'-bpy.

Experimental

All starting chemicals were of A.R. grade except 4,4'-bipyridine which was of reagent grade. Rare earth picrate was prepared according to a literature method¹⁵. Elemental (C, H, N) analyses were carried out with a EL-CHNS-O (German) analyzer. Infrared spectrum (KBr) was measured on a Nicolet 5DXB FT-IR spectrophotometer. Variable magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a Cahn 2000 magnetometer.

$[Tm(H_2O)_4(pic)_2]_2[Tm(H_2O)_6(pic)](4,4'-bpyH)_2(4,4'-bpy)_5(pic)_6$ (**1**) : To Tm(pic)₃·4H₂O (0.3 mmol, 0.2776 g) dissolved in CH₃CN-H₂O (1 : 1, v/v; 10 ml) at 50°, was added CH₃CN-H₂O (1 : 1, v/v; 10 ml) solution containing 4,4'-bipyridine (1.2 mmol) stepwise with stirring, yielding small amount of precipitate. After 20 h, the reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was left to evaporate for one month, giving yellow needle crystals of compound **1**. A single crystal suitable for X-ray analysis was obtained by redissolving the crystals in absolute ethanol and evaporating the solvent at room temperature for 1 month : (Found : C, 37.29; H, 2.47; N, 15.02. Calcd. for C₁₃₆H₁₀₈N₄₇O₉₁Tm₃ : C, 37.44; H, 2.49; N, 15.09%); ν_{max} 3380, 3085, 1862, 1609, 1567, 1539, 1489, 1412, 1363, 1335, 1271, 1215, 1116, 1082, 1039, 1004, 913, 800, 744, 716, 625, 575, 547, 519, 491 cm⁻¹.

$[Gd_2(4,4'-bpy)(pic)_2(H_2O)_{12}](4,4'-bpy)_5(H_2O)_6(pic)_4$ (**2**) : The above-mentioned procedure was repeated using Gd(pic)₃·5H₂O (0.3 mmol, 0.2796 g) as starting material and the reaction temperature was maintained at room temperature : (Found : C, 39.13; H, 3.43; N, 14.51. Calcd. for C₉₆H₉₆N₃₀O₆₀Gd₂ : C, 39.16; H, 3.29; N, 14.27%); ν_{max} 3395, 3085, 1862, 1609, 1567, 1539, 1486, 1412, 1363, 1335, 1271, 1222, 1166, 1082, 1039, 1004, 913, 850, 800, 744, 716, 625, 575, 547, 514, 471 cm⁻¹.

Crystallography : Crystal data were collected on a Siemens P4 diffractometer using graphite-monochromated Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.071073$ nm). The intensities of reflections were measured in the ω -scan mode at 296(2) K. Cell parameters of the complexes were determined from 25 reflections in the θ range of 3.95–17.97° (for compd. **1**) and 26 reflections in the θ range of 2.78–17.21° (for compd. **2**). An empirical absorption correction was applied to the original data set. The structure was solved using direct methods and refined by a full-matrix least-squares on F^2 technique using the SHLXL-97 program package. Hydrogen

atoms of the ligands were generated geometrically.

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